

Supplementary Material

Title: Landscape-level oilseed rape cover shapes seasonal patterns of wild bee abundance in conservation areas

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Supplementary Method

DAG construction, validation and limitations

Directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) provide a framework for causal inference. They allow researchers to estimate causal effects from observational data, taking into account confounding factors and using domain knowledge. The DAG shown in the main text (Figure 2) was developed to represent our assumptions about the causal structure of the study system. We followed Arif and MacNeil (2023) and Ankan et al. (2021) to ensure the appropriateness, construction and validation of the DAG.

In this study, we want to obtain an unbiased estimate of the causal effect of landscape oilseed-rape (OSR) cover on bee abundance in a given grassland patch. It is necessary to condition the model on the confounding local and landscape variables. This yields unbiased estimates for the OSR cover variable but simultaneously biases the estimates for the remaining local and landscape variables by conditioning on their mediators. At the local scale, we assume that bee abundance is affected by factors such as flower cover, nesting site cover, and the area of the habitat patch. At the landscape scale, defined here as the area within a 2 km radius around each focal grassland patch, we consider not only OSR cover but also potential impacts from agricultural practices, captured by the mean field size of annual crops. Finally, bee abundance is also expected to reflect broader regional influences, including geological, topographical, and biogeographical factors, as well as land-use history and climate. These are collectively represented in our model by mean annual temperature. These variables were included in

the model as fixed effects in addition to OSR cover to mitigate potential confounds (Figure S1).

Figure S1. DAG drawn on dagitty.net to test for DAG consistency. Green circles represent exposure variables, blue circle represents the outcome variable, and grey circle represents an unobserved latent variable. Green arrows represent causal paths that are not biased, and grey arrows represent potential but unknown causal relationships.

Additionally, while the relationships between the variables are represented as accurately as possible, some relationships or variables may remain unobserved. For instance, even after accounting for regional effects, grassland patch area might still correlate with landscape-level variables, potentially due to influences from unmeasured latent variables. Similarly, differences in agricultural conditions across landscapes within the same region could function as a shared cause, again implying the existence of an unobserved latent variable. Similarly, differences in agricultural conditions across landscapes within the same region could function as a common cause, again implying the existence of an unobserved latent variable. To account for these potential hidden dependencies between local- and landscape-level variables, we incorporated a latent variable into the DAG (Figure S1).

Once variables were selected and the DAG was constructed based on domain knowledge, the next step was to assess its consistency. This involves verifying whether the independencies implied by the DAG are supported by the observational data. To do so, we employed the R package DAGitty (Textor et al., 2016), which offers a simple method to test whether a DAG is consistent with a data set. As shown in Figure S1, the DAG contains no open biasing paths (green arrows), meaning no further adjustments are required to estimate the total effects of our variables. In the following step, we examined which conditional independencies are implied by the DAG and whether these are reflected in the data. This

was done with the `localTests` function of the `DAGitty` package, which provides the Pearson correlation coefficient, the 95% confidence interval and the p-value for each of the implied conditional independencies. All correlation coefficients were low, and all p-values exceeded 0.05, suggesting that the conditional independencies hold within the data. These results support the conclusion that our DAG is consistent with the observed data and that no strong violations of implied independencies are present.

To further ensure the appropriateness of the DAG, we tested the variables in our DAG for residual spatial autocorrelation. Using the R package “`DHARMA`” (Hartig and Lohse, 2022) with the function `testSpatialAutocorrelation`, we tested the similarity between nearby observations based on Morans I test for distance-based autocorrelation. The results showed no indication of spatial autocorrelation ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that proximity between observations did not lead to correlation. Lastly, we assessed the independent variables in our multiple regression model for multicollinearity. For this, we used the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), a standard measure of multicollinearity, calculated via the `vif()` function from the R package “`car`” (Fox et al., 2001). VIF values for the predictor variable remained below 5, pointing to only moderate correlations, which are generally not problematic and can be disregarded (Akinwande et al., 2015). Higher VIF values (above 5) were only observed for control variables such as “flower cover”; however, since the variable of primary interest (“OSR cover”) did not show elevated VIFs, these higher values were not considered critical.

Although directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) offer several benefits, it is crucial to acknowledge the potential limitations of this method. DAGs rely on assumptions based on domain expertise, existing literature, and researchers’ experience to represent the studied system. Even though they can clarify complex ecological processes, there is no certainty that all underlying assumptions are accurate (Arif and MacNeil, 2023). Because it is nearly impossible to capture every relationship and interaction among influencing variables, and since some variables may remain unidentified or unmeasurable, the ability of DAGs to fully represent an ecological system is inherently constrained. Results should therefore be interpreted with care. Nevertheless, DAGs provide transparency, allowing readers to recognize potential shortcomings or gaps in the current understanding of the system (Arif and MacNeil, 2023). In addition, since DAGs are non-parametric, they do not replace the need for robust statistical model fitting and validation (Digitale et al., 2022). Therefore, thorough testing of the DAG, including checks for consistency with the data and verification of implied independencies, is essential.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S2 Correlation matrix based on Pearson correlation coefficients. Values close to +1 or -1 indicate strong linear relationships between predictor variables, while values near 0 indicate no linear correlation.

Figure S3 Relationships between bee abundance (2022) and OSR cover in 2021 for wild bees during (A) and after OSR flowering (B), bumblebees during OSR flowering (C) and after OSR flowering (D). Solid black lines indicate significant relationships ($p < 0.05$), dashed lines non-significant relationships ($p \geq 0.05$) and grey shaded areas represent the confidence intervals. Points represent the raw data. Regression lines were adjusted for covariates. Abundance (abun.) refers to the number of bees observed within the 1500 m² transect area.

Figure S4 Relationship between wild bee abundance and OSR cover after flowering separated by different life-history traits: body size (A), sociality (B), food specialisation (lecty) (C) and nest position (D). Significant relationships of trait groups with OSR cover are indicated by solid lines ($p < 0.05$), not significant relationships are indicated as dashed lines ($p \geq 0.05$). Shaded areas represent the confidence intervals, points represent the raw data. Regression lines were adjusted for covariates. Abundance (abun.) refers to the number of bees observed within the 1500 m² transect area.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1 Type III analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for the generalized linear models (GLM) assessing the influence of landscape OSR cover (%) in interaction with habitat area, flower cover and nesting site cover on wild bee, endangered wild bee and bumblebee abundance during and after flowering. Nagelkerke's R^2 indicates the proportion of variance explained by the model. Degrees of freedom (Df), test statistics (Chisq) and p -values are shown for each model term. Significant p -values (< 0.05) are shown in bold.

Response	R^2	Variables	Chisq	Df	p
Wild bee abundance	0.813	OSR (%)	0.0052	1	0.9427
		Calc. grassland area	2.4659	1	0.1163
		Flower cover	2.5706	1	0.1089

Response	R ²	Variables	Chisq	Df	p
during OSR flowering		Nesting site cover	0.7533	1	0.3854
		Mean field size	1.6317	1	0.2015
		Mean annual temperature	18.7025	1	<0.0001
		OSR (%) * calc. grassland area	0.3862	1	0.5343
		OSR (%) * flower cover	0.8624	1	0.3531
		OSR (%) * nesting site cover	0.5458	1	0.4600
Wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.421	OSR (%)	2.8538	1	0.0912
		Calc. grassland area	0.0000	1	0.9948
		Flower cover	2.7294	1	0.0985
		Nesting site cover	0.1745	1	0.6762
		Mean field size	0.6100	1	0.4348
		Mean annual temperature	0.0088	1	0.9252
		OSR (%) * calc. grassland area	0.0877	1	0.7671
		OSR (%) * flower cover	1.6204	1	0.2030
		OSR (%) * nesting site cover	3.4471	1	0.0634
Endangered wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.493	OSR (%)	0.3788	1	0.5383
		Calc. grassland area	2.0219	1	0.1551
		Flower cover	0.0681	1	0.7941
		Nesting site cover	3.7122	1	0.0540
		Mean field size	2.0112	1	0.1561
		Mean annual temperature	0.9628	1	0.3265
		OSR (%) * calc. grassland area	3.6173	1	0.0572
		OSR (%) * flower cover	1.5947	1	0.2067
		OSR (%) * nesting site cover	0.0805	1	0.7766
Endangered wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.487	OSR (%)	0.13202	1	0.7164
		Calc. grassland area	0.00001	1	0.9979
		Flower cover	3.13197	1	0.0768
		Nesting site cover	0.76738	1	0.3810
		Mean field size	0.98383	1	0.3213
		Mean annual temperature	0.00788	1	0.9293
		OSR (%) * calc. grassland area	0.98009	1	0.3222

Response	R ²	Variables	Chisq	Df	p
		OSR (%) * flower cover	1.34111	1	0.2468
		OSR (%) * nesting site cover	0.04119	1	0.8392
Bumblebee abundance during OSR flowering	0.758	OSR (%)	2.9194	1	0.0875
		Calc. grassland area	1.4271	1	0.2322
		Flower cover	23.3049	1	<0.0001
		Nesting site cover	1.0059	1	0.3159
		Mean field size	1.1898	1	0.2754
		Mean annual temperature	2.8148	1	0.0934
		OSR (%) * calc. grassland area	0.0563	1	0.8125
		OSR (%) * flower cover	2.4541	1	0.1172
Bumblebee abundance after OSR flowering	0.711	OSR (%)	1.5089	1	0.2193
		Calc. grassland area	7.8247	1	0.0052
		Flower cover	3.3714	1	0.0663
		Nesting site cover	3.7883	1	0.0516
		Mean field size	0.7073	1	0.4003
		Mean annual temperature	10.5999	1	0.0011
		OSR (%) * calc. grassland area	5.5209	1	0.0188
		OSR (%) * flower cover	1.7154	1	0.1903

Table S2 Type II analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for the generalized linear models (GLM) assessing the influence of landscape OSR cover (%) on wild bee and bumblebee abundance during and after flowering. Nagelkerke's R² indicates the proportion of variance explained by the model. Degrees of freedom (Df), test statistics (Chisq) and p-values are shown for each model term. Significant p-values (< 0.05) are shown in bold.

Response	R ²	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
Wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.785	OSR (%)	4.9083	1	0.0267
		Calc. grassland area	3.0878	1	0.0789
		Flower cover	1.9395	1	0.1637
		Nesting site cover	3.8971	1	0.0484
		Mean field size	1.3120	1	0.2520
		Mean annual temperature	17.4479	1	<0.0001
Wild bee abundance	0.294	OSR (%)	3.2984	1	0.0694
		Calc. grassland area	0.0273	1	0.8687
		Flower cover	0.9010	1	0.3425

Response	R ²	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
after OSR flowering		Nesting site cover	4.7531	1	0.0293
		Mean field size	0.5409	1	0.4621
		Mean annual temperature	0.2083	1	0.6481
Endangered wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.404	OSR (%)	1.2453	1	0.2645
		Calc. grassland area	0.0399	1	0.8417
		Flower cover	0.2295	1	0.6319
		Nesting site cover	5.5111	1	0.0189
		Mean field size	2.0050	1	0.1568
		Mean annual temperature	0.6424	1	0.4229
Endangered wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.445	OSR (%)	0.9663	1	0.3256
		Calc. grassland area	1.9905	1	0.1583
		Flower cover	4.7885	1	0.0287
		Nesting site cover	1.6220	1	0.2028
		Mean field size	1.1690	1	0.2796
		Mean annual temperature	0.3553	1	0.5511
Bumblebee abundance during OSR flowering	0.712	OSR (%)	0.4857	1	0.4859
		Calc. grassland area	5.3448	1	0.0208
		Flower cover	25.0076	1	<0.0001
		Nesting site cover	0.9380	1	0.3328
		Mean field size	1.5340	1	0.2155
		Mean annual temperature	2.3675	1	0.1239
Bumblebee abundance after OSR flowering	0.619	OSR (%)	4.0513	1	0.0441
		Calc. grassland area	2.1040	1	0.1469
		Flower cover	3.5379	1	0.0600
		Nesting site cover	4.1141	1	0.0425
		Mean field size	1.2510	1	0.2634
		Mean annual temperature	13.2471	1	0.0003

Table S3 Type III analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for the generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) assessing the influence of landscape OSR cover (%) in interaction with wild bee life-history traits on wild bee abundance during and after flowering.

Conditional R^2 indicates the proportion of variance explained by the model. Degrees of freedom (Df), test statistics (Chisq) and p-values are shown for each model term. Significant p-values (< 0.05) are shown in bold.

Response	R^2	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
Social vs solitary wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.756	Intercept	16.9792	1	<0.0001
		OSR (%)	10.4780	1	<0.0001
		Sociality	49.1930	1	<0.0001
		Calc. grassland area	1.8992	1	0.1682
		Flower cover	15.3088	1	<0.0001
		Nesting site cover	0.3151	1	0.5746
		Mean field size	0.6075	1	0.4357
		Mean annual temperature	1.6268	1	0.2022
		OSR (%) * sociality	8.0206	1	0.0046
Social vs solitary wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.668	Intercept	0.0709	1	0.7900
		OSR (%)	2.0213	1	0.1551
		Sociality	22.6859	1	<0.0001
		Calc. grassland area	0.0146	1	0.9040
		Flower cover	2.6475	1	0.1037
		Nesting site cover	0.4972	1	0.4807
		Mean field size	1.3370	1	0.2476
		Mean annual temperature	1.2237	1	0.2686
		OSR (%) * sociality	0.2695	1	0.6037
Small vs large wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.560	Intercept	5.4937	1	0.0191
		OSR (%)	0.2809	1	0.5961
		Body size	8.0514	1	0.0046
		Calc. grassland area	2.2120	1	0.1369
		Flower cover	0.5578	1	0.4551
		Nesting site cover	3.3170	1	0.0686
		Mean field size	0.6606	1	0.4164
		Mean annual temperature	13.5768	1	0.0002
		OSR (%) * body size	3.4459	1	0.0634
Small vs large wild bee	0.263	Intercept	1.3099	1	0.2524
		OSR (%)	4.9424	1	0.0262
		Body size	3.6342	1	0.0566

Response	R ²	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
abundance after OSR flowering		Calc. grassland area	0.4603	1	0.4975
		Flower cover	4.1819	1	0.0409
		Nesting site cover	1.3411	1	0.2468
		Mean field size	0.2024	1	0.6528
		Mean annual temperature	0.4326	1	0.5107
		OSR (%) * body size	2.2398	1	0.1345
Poly- vs oligolectic wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.665	Intercept	6.2679	1	0.0123
		OSR (%)	0.0733	1	0.7866
		Food specialization	13.8568	1	0.0002
		Calc. grassland area	3.1341	1	0.0767
		Flower cover	0.0252	1	0.8738
		Nesting site cover	0.0486	1	0.8256
		Mean field size	0.8713	1	0.3506
		Mean annual temperature	9.0726	1	0.0026
Poly- vs oligolectic wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.595	Intercept	0.0003	1	0.9868
		OSR (%)	1.3860	1	0.2391
		Food specialization	16.1655	1	<0.0001
		Calc. grassland area	0.5094	1	0.4754
		Flower cover	2.6070	1	0.1064
		Nesting site cover	0.0149	1	0.9027
		Mean field size	0.0661	1	0.7971
		Mean annual temperature	1.4046	1	0.2360
Under- vs aboveground nesting wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	NA	Intercept	10.6472	1	0.001
		OSR (%)	0.3690	1	0.5436
		Nest position	6.9125	1	0.0086
		Calc. grassland area	1.7581	1	0.1849
		Flower cover	0.9995	1	0.3175
		Nesting site cover	0.0259	1	0.8722
		Mean field size	5.4258	1	0.0198

Response	R ²	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
		Mean annual temperature	15.7283	1	<0.0001
		OSR (%) * nest position	0.9852	1	0.3209
Under- vs aboveground nesting wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.366	Intercept	0.8001	1	0.3711
		OSR (%)	2.4120	1	0.1204
		Nest position	13.0736	1	0.0003
		Calc. grassland area	0.3611	1	0.5480
		Flower cover	2.2031	1	0.1377
		Nesting site cover	0.2309	1	0.6309
		Mean field size	0.0058	1	0.9392
		Mean annual temperature	3.2432	1	0.0717
		OSR (%) * nest position	1.7038	1	0.1918

Table S4 Type II analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for the generalized linear models (GLM) assessing the influence of landscape OSR cover of 2021 (%) wild bee and bumblebee abundance during and after flowering. Nagelkerke's R² indicates the proportion of variance explained by the model. Degrees of freedom (Df), test statistics (Chisq) and p-values are shown for each model term. Significant p-values (< 0.05) are shown in bold.

Response	R ²	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
Wild bee abundance during OSR flowering	0.771	OSR 2021 (%)	3.8287	1	0.0504
		Calc. grassland area	5.1148	1	0.0237
		Flower cover	2.9259	1	0.0872
		Nesting site cover	6.7206	1	0.0095
		Mean field size	1.2079	1	0.2717
		Mean annual temperature	15.4908	1	<0.0001
Wild bee abundance after OSR flowering	0.253	OSR 2021 (%)	1.8690	1	0.1716
		Calc. grassland area	0.1447	1	0.7037
		Flower cover	0.2470	1	0.6192
		Nesting site cover	3.4826	1	0.0620
		Mean field size	0.2922	1	0.5888
		Mean annual temperature	0.5068	1	0.4765
Bumblebee abundance	0.707	OSR 2021 (%)	0.0022	1	0.9624
		Calc. grassland area	4.6241	1	0.0315
		Flower cover	24.7691	1	<0.0001

Response	R ²	Variable	Chisq	Df	p
during OSR flowering		Nesting site cover	1.6062	1	0.2050
		Mean field size	2.3707	1	0.1236
		Mean annual temperature	2.1000	1	0.1473
Bumblebee abundance after OSR flowering	0.590	OSR 2021 (%)	2.4238	1	0.1195
		Calc. grassland area	1.2583	1	0.2620
		Flower cover	5.1287	1	0.0235
		Nesting site cover	2.9793	1	0.0843
		Mean field size	0.7040	1	0.4015
		Mean annual temperature	11.3630	1	0.0008

Table S5 Comparison of Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) between models including landscape OSR cover from 2022 (sampling year) and 2021 (previous year). AIC values allow comparison of model fit; lower AIC indicates a better-fitting model.

Model	AIC 2022	AIC 2021
MAY Wild bee abundance ~ OSR cover * calc. grassland area + OSR cover * flower cover + OSR cover * nesting site cover + Mean field size + Mean annual temperature	323.316	323.221
JUNE Wild bee abundance ~ OSR cover * calc. grassland area + OSR cover * flower cover + OSR cover * nesting site cover + Mean field size + Mean annual temperature	361.124	363.378
MAY Bumblebee abundance ~ OSR cover * calc. grassland area + OSR cover * flower cover + nesting site cover + Mean field size + Mean annual temperature	231.017	231.098
JUNE bumblebee abundance ~ OSR cover * calc. grassland area + OSR cover * flower cover + nesting site cover + Mean field size + Mean annual temperature	334.820	360.964
MAY Wild bee abundance ~ OSR cover +	319.645	320.597

calc. grassland area +		
flower cover +		
nesting site cover +		
Mean field size +		
Mean annual temperature		
<hr/>		
JUNE Wild bee abundance ~		
OSR cover +		
calc. grassland area +		
flower cover +	359.613	360.964
nesting site cover +		
Mean field size +		
Mean annual temperature		
<hr/>		
MAY Bumblebee abundance ~		
OSR cover +		
calc. grassland area +		
flower cover +	229.749	230.232
nesting site cover +		
Mean field size +		
Mean annual temperature		
<hr/>		
JUNE Bumblebee abundance ~		
OSR cover +		
calc. grassland area +		
flower cover +	336.019	337.554
nesting site cover +		
Mean field size +		
Mean annual temperature		

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